

THE LEVEL OF AWARENESS OF THE GRADE 12 SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF FAR EASTERN UNIVERSITY - NICANOR REYES MEDICAL FOUNDATION ON INDOOR POLLUTANTS AND ITS EFFECTS ON HEALTH

Gheecel Micah P. Cerbas, Pia Katherine A. Baleyos, Shaira Marielle Carla M. Baquiran, Reoh B. Daños, Samantha Mecole D. Gualberto, Ma. Celina E. Nadonga, Ivan Fredric U. Caiña, Bea Patricia L. Custodio

School of Respiratory Therapy, Far Eastern University Nicanor Reyes Medical Foundation, West Fairview, Quezon City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Indoor air pollution (IAP) is a global health concern affecting millions. Recent estimates indicate IAP significantly contributes to mortality and illness in severely impacted nations, with approximately 1.2 million annual fatalities linked to exposure.³ Sources of IAP include combustion appliances, tobacco smoke, and household products, emitting hazardous pollutants like carbon monoxide and particulate matter.⁶ These are associated with serious conditions like pneumonia, chronic respiratory diseases, heart disease, and lung cancer.² This cross-sectional study explores the knowledge of Grade 12 - Senior High School students of Far Eastern University – Nicanor Reyes Medical Foundation (FEU-NRMF) on IAP, between sex, age, and its health effects. 80 out of 86 students completed an online survey via Google Forms and using a Likert scale. The study found that age does not significantly affect awareness of IAP sources ($p = 0.14$); health effects ($p = 0.68$), as both p -values exceeded the $\alpha = 0.05$. Similarly, sex has no significant influence on awareness of IAP sources ($p = 0.055$); health effects ($p = 0.98$), with p -values surpassing the predetermined alpha level. These values suggest that age and sex are not predictors of awareness regarding IAP. There is insufficient evidence to definitely state that demographic factors do not influence the awareness levels of IAP among senior high school students. This insufficiency stems from the imbalance in respondent numbers. The researchers recommend that future studies aim for a more balanced count of respondents of both sexes and ages to provide a more accurate assessment.

Keywords: *Indoor air pollution (IAP), Indoor air quality (IAQ), Sick building syndrome (SBS), Monoterpenes, Nitrogen Oxide*

INTRODUCTION

Approximately 3.2 million people experience premature death due to indoor air pollution resulting from the utilization of solid fuels and kerosene for cooking. To elaborate further, the majority of individuals exposed to indoor air pollution suffer from ischemic heart disease, accounting for around 32% of cases, followed by strokes at 23%. Additionally, 21% of cases are attributed to lower respiratory infections, particularly affecting young children aged five years and below who are at a higher risk, often experiencing pneumonia primarily affecting their lower respiratory systems. Moreover, 19% of cases are linked to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), with a higher incidence in middle-income countries due to increased susceptibility to household air pollution. Lung cancer accounts for approximately 6% of cases, largely associated with the use of kerosene, wood, and charcoal as energy sources for cooking (World Health Organization (WHO), 2021).⁵ Indoor air pollution stems from a multitude of indoor activities, including the use of combustion appliances that burn fuels, tobacco products, building materials, and furnishings such as newly installed floors, upholstery, carpets, and wood-based furniture. It is important to identify what types and kinds are inside the house to know the source of indoor pollutants - as it involves harmful pollutants such as carbon monoxide (CO), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), particulate matter (PM), aerosol, biological pollutants, and others.⁴ Additionally, household cleaning and maintenance products like air fresheners, personal care items such as hairspray, nail polish, and perfume, as well as the operation of air conditioning units and humidification devices, contribute to indoor air pollution.⁷ Generally, few studies have focused on how people consume their time indoors, in which good indoor air quality is significant to each individual's health. There are various sources of air pollutants that can notably be observed indoors, including the materials and fuels that have been consumed in daily human activities (Leung, 2014).⁸ It is crucial to give attention regarding indoor pollution to further understand the causes and effects to human health and draw necessary actions in preventing adverse-health effects. Indoor air pollutants contribute to millions of deaths (Housing Reference Manual, 2012).¹ This study aims to expand knowledge about indoor pollutants. Awareness of indoor pollutants is significant to homeowners as this can provide an opportunity for them to identify, and control the sources of pollutants, and maintain proper ventilation, and air-filtration systems.

The primary objective of this study is to assess the awareness levels of Far Eastern University - Nicanor Reyes Medical Foundation (FEU-NRMF) senior high school students regarding indoor pollutants present in their respective households. This research can be a medium of information for the definition, types, health effects, and management of inhaled indoor pollutants; such as the known effects of inhaling indoor pollutants may lead to noncommunicable diseases such as stroke, ischemic heart disease, chronic obstructive diseases (COPDs), and even lung cancer. (WHO, 2022)¹¹

This research is only limited to Grade 12 - Senior High School students of FEU-NRMF. The participants are only within the vicinity of the researchers' institution because of the given restraint due to time and budget. The data gathered from respondents are about their awareness regarding indoor pollutants and its health effects, including the association of basic demographics such as age and sex. The researchers did not infer whether each participant had an underlying condition when answering the survey questionnaire. This research is very timely given that many people consume their time indoors for a long period. The study is conducted in the 1st semester of the Academic Year 2023 - 2024.

The study seeks to contribute to the broader understanding of indoor pollutants, and how it adversely impacts one's health. Recognizing and understanding indoor pollutants is crucial for the residents, as it enables them to identify and take control of potential sources of pollution. Additionally, it empowers them to maintain proper ventilation and utilize effective air-filtration systems, thereby fostering healthier indoor environments.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the awareness and knowledge of Grade 12 Senior High School students from Far Eastern University - Dr. Nicanor Reyes Medical Foundation about indoor pollutants. Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the demographic characteristics of the participants?
 - 1.1 Age in years
 - 1.2 Sex
 2. What is the level of awareness of the Grade 12 students regarding the types of indoor pollutants that can be inhaled inside the household?
 - 2.1 LPG
 - 2.2 Smoke
 - 2.3 Mold
 - 2.4 Dust
 - 2.5 Pests (e.g. droppings of cockroaches, dust mites, and alike)
 - 2.6 Pets
 - 2.7 Cleaning products
 3. What is the level of awareness of the Grade 12 students regarding the effects of inhalation of indoor pollutants on health?
 - 3.1 Respiratory illness
 - 3.2 Heart disease
 - 3.3 Allergy
 - 3.4 Eye irritation
 - 3.5 Infection
 - 3.6 Indoor air pollution has no effect on health
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METHODOLOGY

The participants will be all Grade 12 Senior High School students of the FEU-NRMF School Year 2023 – 2024. The stated university is located at Regalado Avenue, Fairview, Quezon City, Metro Manila, 1118. The research method used to gather the data is a quantitative type of research which statistically analyzes the data, with the use of online survey questionnaires through Google Forms. The 4th-Year researchers from School of Respiratory Therapy distributed the forms using purposive sampling since all of Grade 12 students are the participants, a sample of all eighty-six (86), and a total of eighty (80) who answered the online survey questionnaire.

The respondents will be recruited using a purposive sampling technique due to its flexibility for the researchers among the non-probability sampling techniques, and because of the accessibility of the gathering of the information from the participants this facilitates the purpose of the study. The respondents of this study are limited to all eighty- six (86) students of Grade 12 Senior High School of FEU-NRMF, for the School Year of 2023-2024. The study used an online survey questionnaire created using Google Forms. The source or guide that was used to create the questionnaire was the Assessment of Risks from Combined Exposure to Multiple Chemicals in Indoor Air by the World Health Organization (WHO).¹¹

The data were gathered by collecting each student's survey questionnaire that was disseminated to the eighty- six (86) respondents from Grade 12 Senior High School students of FEU-NRMF. It was noted that it will take three (3) to five (5) minutes of their time to complete the online survey questionnaire.

The research instrument consisted of 2 parts: the first part details the demographic characteristics (age, sex, and section) of the respondents. The second part is a 14-item questionnaire on IAP and its effects on health (9 items on the sources of IAP and 5 items on the effects of IAP on health). Each item will be answered according to the respondents' level of awareness using the Like scale: 5 – Strongly Agree, 4 – Agree, 3 – Undecided, 2 – Disagree, and 1 – Strongly Disagree. It will take approximately three (3) to five (5) minutes to accomplish the questionnaire.

The survey questionnaires were collected, tallied and computed. The gathered data was analyzed and interpreted showing the results in a table form. The researchers used the weighted mean in this study to determine the level of awareness of the eighty- six (86) students from the Grade 12 Senior High School Students of FEU-NRMF Academic Year 2022-2023 on inhaling indoor pollutants in their respective households. The weighted mean formula is used to calculate the average of all answers.

Weighted mean:

$$\mu = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

Where:

μ = Weighted mean

X = the respondent's answer

N = total number of scores drawn

Chi-square Independence Test:

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(o - e)^2}{e}$$

The Chi-square independence test is to check whether two variables are related or not, this is to draw conclusions from a population.

To obtain the chi-squared value, first calculate the accumulated value from the responses of the participants which is the observed value (O). Expected value (E) is calculated by multiplying the row total with the column total and divided by the overall total. The difference between the expected value and observed value is obtained by subtracting the expected value from the observed value and squaring it and dividing it by the expected value. The chi-squared value is attained by adding all up the values from the difference of observed and expected value and by squaring it. The degrees of freedom then are calculated by subtracting the number of rows to 1 and multiplying the answer to the difference of the number of columns and 1. The p-value is calculated from the deviation of the observed and the reference value.

O = observed value

E = expected value

Expected value:

$$\frac{\text{Column total} \times \text{Row total}}{\text{Grand total}}$$

$(O-E)^2/E$ = the difference between observed and the expected value

x^2 = chi-squared value **df** = degrees of freedom

$$df = (c - 1) (r - 1)$$

p-value = probability value

α = alpha significance level of 5% or 0.05

H₀= null hypothesis implies that there is no difference between groups or no relationship between variables

H_1 = alternative hypothesis implies that there is significant relationship between the variables

The scope of this study consists of Grade 12 - Senior High School students of FEU-NRMF. The participants are within the researchers' institution because of the given restraint due to time and budget. The data gathered from respondents are about their awareness regarding IAP and its health effects, including basic demographics like age and sex. The study is conducted in the 1st semester of the Academic Year 2023 - 2024.

RESULTS

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of 86 Grade 12 Senior High School students at the FEU-NRMF.

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
AGE IN YEARS		
16	11	11.6%
17	42	48.8%
18	32	37.2%
19	1	1.2%
TOTAL	80	98.8% or 100%
SEX		
Male	24	27.9%
Female	62	72.1%
TOTAL	80	100%

Table 2. Level of awareness of 86 Grade 12 Senior High School students at the FEU-NRMF on the sources of indoor air pollution.

SOURCE S OF IAP	STRONG LY AGREE	AGREE	UNDECID ED	DISAGR EE	STRONG LY DISAGR EE	TOTAL
Stoves using liquified petroleum gas (LPG)	14	43	15	7	1	80
Air conditioner	7	32	24	13	4	80
Paints	18	39	13	9	1	80
Pets	11	34	22	10	3	80
Insects and pests	21	35	15	8	1	80
Cleaning products	22	36	16	4	2	80
Cigarette smoke	62	16	0	1	1	80

Molds	36	32	8	2	2	80
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Table 3. Level of awareness of 86 Grade 12 Senior High School students at the FEU-NRMF on the effects of indoor air pollution on health.

EFFECTS OF IAP	STRONGLY AGREE	AGRE E	UNDECID ED	DISAGR EE	STRONGLY DISAGREE	TOTAL
Respiratory diseases	50	28	2	0	0	80
Heart diseases	24	35	20	1	0	80
Allergy	50	28	1	1	0	80
Irritation	48	31	1	0	0	80
Infections	38	28	9	5	0	80
IAP has no effect on health	6	3	4	20	47	80

Table 4.1 Level of Awareness according to the Gender; Sources of IAP

Observed (O)						
3. SEX AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS IN THE SOURCES OF INDOOR AIR POLLUTION						
GENDE R	Extremely Aware	Moderately Aware	Undecided	Slightly Aware	Unaware	
Male	1	12	9	0	0	22
Female	6	46	5	1	0	58
	7	58	14	1	0	80

Table 4.2 Level of Awareness according to the Age; Sources of IAP

Observed (O)						
1. AGE AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS IN THE SOURCES OF INDOOR AIR POLLUTION						
AGE	Extremely Aware	Moderately Aware	Undecided	Slightly Aware	Unaware	
16	1	5	2	1	0	9
17	4	26	10	0	0	40
18	2	26	2	0	0	30
19	0	0	1	0	0	1
	7	57	15	1	0	80

Table 4.3 Level of Awareness according to the Sex; Health Effects of IAP

Observed (O)						
4. SEX AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS ON HEALTH EFFECTS						
GENDE R	Extremely Aware	Moderately Aware	Undecided	Slightly Aware	Unaware	
Male	10	12	0	0	0	22
Female	31	27	0	0	0	58
	41	39	0	0	0	80

Table 4.4 Level of Awareness according to the Age; Health Effects of IAP

Observed (O)						
2. AGE AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS ON HEALTH EFFECTS						
AGE	Extremely A	Moderately /	Undecided	Slightly Aw	Unaware	
16	1	8	0	0	0	9
17	21	20	0	0	0	41
18	19	10	0	0	0	29
19	0	1	0	0	0	1
	41	39	0	0	0	80

Table 4.5 Level of Awareness according to the Age; Sources of IAP: Hypothesis

Expected €					
1. AGE AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS IN THE SOURCES OF INDOOR AIR POLLUTION					
AGE	Extremely Aware	Moderately Aware	Undecided	Slightly Aware	Unaware
16	0.7875	6.4125	1.6875	0.1125	0
17	3.5	28.5	7.5	0.5	0
18	2.625	21.375	5.625	0.375	0
19	0.0875	0.7125	0.1875	0.0125	0

(O-E) ² /E					
1. AGE AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS IN THE SOURCES OF INDOOR AIR POLLUTION					
AGE	Extremely Aware	Moderately Aware	Undecided	Slightly Aware	Unaware
16	0.05734127	0.311135478	0.05787037	7.0013889	0
17	0.071428571	0.219298246	0.833333333	0.5	0
18	0.148809524	1.000730994	2.336111111	0.375	0
19	0.0875	0.7125	3.520833333	0.0125	0
x ²	17.24578112				
df	12				
p-value	0.140583407				

Table 4.6 Level of Awareness according to the Age; Health Effects of IAP: Hypothesis

Expected €					
2. AGE AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS ON HEALTH EFFECTS					
AGE	Extremely A	Moderately A	Undecided	Slightly Awa	Unaware
16	4.6125	4.3875	0	0	0
17	21.0125	19.9875	0	0	0
18	14.8625	14.1375	0	0	0
19	0.5125	0.4875	0	0	0

Table 4.7 Level of Awareness according to the Sex; Sources of IAP: Hypothesis

$(O-E)^2/E$					
2. AGE AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS ON HEALTH EFFECTS					
AGE	Extremely Aw	Moderately Aw	Undecided	Slightly Aw	Unaware
16	2.829302168	2.974394587	0	0	0
17	7.43605E-06	7.81739E-06	0	0	0
18	1.151818755	1.210886384	0	0	0
19	0.5125	0.538782051	0	0	0
x ²	9.217699199				
df	12				
p-value =	0.684232137				

Table 4.8 Level of Awareness according to the Sex; Sources of IAP: Hypothesis

Expected €					
3. SEX AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS IN THE SOURCES OF INDOOR AIR POLLUTION					
GENDER	Extremely Aware	Moderately Aware	Undecided	Slightly Aware	Unaware
Male	1.925	15.95	3.85	0.275	0
Female	5.075	42.05	10.15	0.725	0
$(O-E)^2/E$					
3. SEX AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS IN THE SOURCES OF INDOOR AIR POLLUTION					
GENDER	Extremely Aware	Moderately Aware	Undecided	Slightly Aware	Unaware
Male	0.444480519	0.978213166	6.88896104	0.275	0
Female	0.168596059	0.371046373	0.00110837	0.1043103	0
x ²	9.231715876				
df	4				
p-value	0.055561566				

Table 4.9 Level of Awareness according to the Sex; Health Effects of IAP: Hypothesis

Expected €					
4. SEX AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS ON HEALTH EFFECTS					
GENDER	Extremely Aware	Moderately Aware	Undecided	Slightly Aware	Unaware
Male	11.275	10.725	0	0	0
Female	29.725	28.275	0	0	0

(O-E) ² /E					
4. SEX AND LEVEL OF AWARENESS ON HEALTH EFFECTS					
GENDE	Extremely Aware	Moderately Aware	Undecided	Slightly Aware	Unaware
Male	0.144179601	0.151573427	0	0	0
Female	0.054688814	0.057493369	0	0	0
x ²	0.40793521				
df	4				
p-value	0.981822084				

DISCUSSION

Table 1: Grade 12 Senior High School Students consists of 62 females with it being the majority and 24 males with a total of 80. The table provides an overview of the demographic distribution among grade 12 students at FEU-NRMF for the academic year 2023-2024, categorized by age groups. Majority of the population comprises 48.8% of the total population, corresponding to students aged 17 years old. Conversely, a significant proportion, constituting 37.2%, pertains to individuals in the 18-year-old age bracket. Additionally, a demographic subset of 16-years olds is represented at 12.8%, while the minority of the student population, accounting for 1.2%, falls within the age group of 19 years old. Both a total of 100%.

Table 2: Shows the sources of indoor air pollution comprising a total 191 for the 'Strongly Agree'; 267 for 'Agree' which is the majority of the responses; '113' for the 'Undecided'; 54 for senior high school students answered 'Disagree'; and the least being 15, responded 'Strongly Disagree'.

Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG): it shows that 43 individuals, constituting 53.8% of the respondents, agree with the notion that LPG is a source of indoor air pollution. Air conditioners: it is indicated that 32 individuals or 40% of the population align with the idea that air conditioners can contribute to indoor air pollution.

Paint: 39 respondents, equivalent to 48.8% of the surveyed population, agree with the notion that paint has the potential to contribute to indoor air pollution.

Pets: it is highlighted that 34 respondents, constituting 42.5% of the surveyed population, agree with the idea that pests contribute to indoor air pollution.

Pests: it is emphasized that 35 respondents, making up 43.8% of the surveyed population, agree that insects and pests possess the potential to contribute to indoor air pollution.

Cleaning products: 36 respondents, representing 45% of the population, express agreement with the idea that cleaning products serve as a contributor to indoor air pollution.

Cigarette smoke: 62 respondents, comprising 77.5% of the population, agree with the notion that cigarette smoke contributes to indoor air pollution.

Molds: it is evident that 36 respondents making up 45% of the population agree with the notion that molds are a factor in indoor air pollution.

Table 3: SOS 1: To describe the demographic characteristics of Grade 12 Senior High School students of the FEU-NRMF as to;

Majority answered with 'Strongly Agree' with a total of 216, then a total of 153 with 'Agree', 37 with 'Undecided', 27 with 'Disagree', 47 with 'Strongly Agree'.

Respiratory disease: 50 respondents comprising 62.5% of the population, strongly agree that respiratory disease can result from indoor air pollution.

Heart disease: 35 respondents making up 43.8% of the population agree with the concept that heart disease can be an outcome of indoor air pollution.

Allergy: 50 individuals, equivalent to 62.5% of the surveyed population strongly agree with the notion that allergy can result from indoor air pollution.

Eye irritation: it is emphasized that 48 respondents, making up to 60% of the population strongly agree that irritation can result from indoor air pollution.

Infection: it is evident that 38 respondents constituting 47.5% of the population, strongly agree that infection can result from indoor air pollution.

No effect(s) on health: 47 participants comprising 58.8% of the population strongly disagree that indoor air pollution has no effect on health.

Table 4.1: SOS 2: To determine their level of awareness on the Sources of IAP; Majority of the Grade 12 Senior High School students are 'Moderately Aware' followed by 'Undecided', then 'Extremely Aware', a single respondent with 'Slightly Aware' and no respondent is Unaware.

Table 4.2: Most of the Grade 12 Senior High School who are 'Moderately Aware' regarding the age and the level of awareness in the sources of Indoor Air Pollution,

followed by 'Undecided' with a total of 15, then Extremely Aware with 7, then a single respondent who is 'Slightly Aware'. None are 'Unaware'.

Table 4.3: SOS 3: To determine their level of awareness on the Health Effects of IAP; As for sex and level of awareness on health effects, the majority of the Females are 'Extremely Aware' with 'Moderately Aware' being next. In Males, 'Moderately Aware' have 12 and there are 10 that are 'Extremely Aware' None are 'Undecided', 'Slightly Aware' and 'Unaware' in both genders.

Table 4.4: SOS 4: To describe the association between demographic characteristics and level of awareness on IAP and its effects on health.

$p > 0.05$ = accept the H_0

$p < 0.05$ = reject the H_0

In age and level of awareness on health effects, Majority are 'Extremely Aware' and 17-year-olds, then 18-year-olds followed by 'Moderately Aware'.

Table 4.5: H_0 : Age has no effect or influence on the level of awareness of IAP H_1 : Age has an effect or influence on the level of awareness of IAP. In this case, the researchers has accepted the null hypothesis with the p-value of 0.14 that exceeds the $\alpha = 0.05$ or 5%. Hence, age has no effect or influence on the level of awareness of IAP regarding the sources of IAP.

Table 4.6: H_0 : Age has no effect or influence on the level of awareness of IAP. H_1 : Age has an effect or influence on the level of awareness of IAP. In this case, the researchers has accepted the null hypothesis with the p-value of 0.14 that exceeds the $\alpha = 0.05$ or 5%. Hence, age has no effect or influence on the level of awareness of IAP regarding the sources of IAP.

Table 4.7: H_0 : Age has no effect or influence on the level of awareness on health effects

H_1 : Age has an effect or influence on the level of awareness on health effects. In this case, the p-value is 0.68 which is more than the alpha significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the researchers has accepted the null hypothesis, age has no effect or influence on the level of awareness of IAP regarding the effects on health.

Table 4.8: H_0 : Gender has no effect or influence on the level of awareness of IAP.

H_1 : Gender has an effect or influence on the level of awareness of IAP

In this case, the p-value is 0.055 or 0.06 which is greater than the alpha significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the researchers has accepted the null hypothesis, sex has no effect or influence on the level of awareness of IAP regarding the sources of IAP.

Table 4.9: H_0 : Gender has no effect or influence on the level of awareness on health effects. H_1 : Gender has an effect or influence on the level of awareness on health effects

In this case, the p-value is 0.98 which is greater than the alpha significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the researchers have accepted the null hypothesis, sex has no effect or influence on the level of awareness of IAP regarding the effects on health.

Conclusions

The goal of the research was to determine the Level of Awareness of Grade 12 Senior High School students of FEU-NRMF on indoor pollutants and their health effects. The results from the chi-square independence test showed that they are moderately aware of indoor pollution and its health effects. Furthermore, the hypothesis that states age has no significant effect or influence on the level of awareness of indoor air pollution, is accepted. sex has no effect or influence on the level of awareness in indoor air pollution, hence, the hypothesis is accepted.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the researcher's recommendations are made:

1. Further propagate awareness of indoor air pollution and strengthen knowledge among younger children and the general public. It is essential to integrate comprehensive educational programs in school curricula that educate students about the sources, health effects, and preventive measures related to indoor air pollutants.
2. There is not enough evidence to conclude that demographics by sex of the senior high school students solely affect their level of awareness in the IAP due to the few counts of males with a total of 22 respondents compared to the females who are 58 students. The researchers suggest that future researchers should consider taking more respondents with males and females to have a more proportionate value.
3. Factors may or may not be limited to age, gender, social environment, physical or mental factors that would influence this awareness and how the participants react to it.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The respondents who participated in the study had been provided by the researchers with a consent form before giving out questionnaires, to which the respondents could have the decision whether to participate in the study, stated in the form as well as assurance to respect their decision without pressure or coercion and that participation is completely voluntary. In regards to the Data Privacy Law, all of the information gathered from the respondents, its privacy, and anonymity is strictly implemented and is only used, discussed, and assessed in this study. If agreement was reached and consent was given, even while answering or participating, one can still have the right to opt-out.

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REFERENCES

- Bower, J. (2019, February 1). *Chapter 5: Indoor Air Pollutants and Toxic Materials*. Healthy Housing Reference Manual.NCEH. Retrieved February 27 2023 from <https://www.cdc.gov/nceh/publications/books/housing/cha05.htm>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2023a, July 31). *What are the risk factors for lung cancer?*. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/lung/basic_info/risk_factors.htm
- Environmental Protection Agency. (n.d.). *Introduction to Indoor Air Quality*. EPA. Retrieved March 15, 2023, from <https://www.epa.gov/indoor-air-quality-iaq/introduction-indoor-air-quality>
- Indoor Air can cause health problems. *Indoor Air Can Cause Health Problems* Health Encyclopedia - University of Rochester Medical Center. (n.d.). Retrieved February 6, 2023, from <https://www.urmc.rochester.edu/encyclopedia/content.aspx?ContentTypeID=1&ContentID=2163>
- Ph ranks 2nd in Asia-Pacific in deaths due to household pollution. (n.d.). https://faspselib.denr.gov.ph/sites/default/files//180503_INQnet_PH%20ranks%202nd%20in%20Asia-Pacific%20in%20deaths%20due%20to%20household%20pollution.pdf
- Tran, V. V., Park, D., & Lee, Y.-C. (2020, April 23). *Indoor air pollution, related human diseases, and recent trends in the control and improvement of Indoor Air Quality*. MDPI. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/17/8/2927>
- World Health Organization.(n.d.). *Household air pollution*. World Health Organization. Retrieved January 31, 2023, from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/household-air-pollution-and-health>

- World Health Organization.(n.d.). *Household air pollution*. World Health Organization. Retrieved March 21, 2023, from [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/household-air-pollution-and-health#:~:text=Household%20air%20pollution%20exposure%20leads,\(COPD\)%20and%20young%20cancer.](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/household-air-pollution-and-health#:~:text=Household%20air%20pollution%20exposure%20leads,(COPD)%20and%20young%20cancer.)
- World Health Organization.(n.d.). *Household air pollution*. World Health Organization. Retrieved January 31, 2023, from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/household-air-pollution-and-health>
- World Health Organization.(n.d.). *Household air pollution*.World Health Organization. Retrieved January 31, [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/household-air-pollution-andhealth#:~:text=The%20combined%20effects%20of%20ambient,\(COPD\)%20and%20young%20cancer.](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/household-air-pollution-andhealth#:~:text=The%20combined%20effects%20of%20ambient,(COPD)%20and%20young%20cancer.)
- World Health Organization. (n.d.-b). *Screening questionnaire for selection of sampling sites for assessment of risks from combined exposure to multiple chemicals in indoor air*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/9789289055635>